

NETWORKING AND COLLABORATION AMONG SOCIAL WELFARE ORGANISATIONS IN MIZORAM

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The present paper discusses the patterns of collaboration and networking among the VOs on the one hand and between VOs and GOs on the other in Aizawl, the state capital of Mizoram. As a backdrop to this in this study an attempt has been made to describe the characteristics of VOs, their organisational structure and pattern of service delivery. An attempt has also been made to identify the major constraints to interorganisational collaboration and networking among VOs from their leaders' perspective.

Collaboration and networking have a significant role to play on resolving the problems of the community especially in today's world when the services and activities have become more diversified and specialised. At macro level interorganisational collaboration is a strategy for those who work in community building, civic culture, local-level problem resolution, and democratic citizen participation (see Austin, 1991; Gates, 1991; Gray, 1989). The growing number of cooperative ventures such as partnerships, alliances, and networks suggests that organisations are learning to work together and are benefiting from the new institutional arrangements.

Collaboration is a cooperative, inter-organisational relationship that relies on neither market nor hierarchical mechanisms of control (Ouchi, 1980). In their groundbreaking multisector study of inter-organisational collaboration, Alter and Hage (1993) defined a network as "the basic social form that permits inter-organisational interactions of exchange, concerted action, and joint production. Networks are unbounded or bounded clusters of organisations that, by definition, are non-hierarchical collectives of legally separate units" (Alter and Hage, 1993:46). According to them the network has four characteristics: (1) cognitive structures with a mutually shared conceptual framework held by individuals with common goals and methods; (2) non-hierarchical structures with lateral linkages and joint decision making that facilitate equal status among member organisations and reduce conflicts; (3) a division of labour in which each unit brings a technical and compatible competence to the relationship; and (4) self-regulation in the production of a new service.

There is copious literature both theoretical and empirical by a wide spectrum of social scientists especially social workers and administrators in the west. This literature has concentrated either on the organisational level or on community studies in the west. Management studies have examined large, visible, and usually public bureaucracies that come together to coordinate and integrate services in a specific field, such as corrections, child welfare, mental health, or education (see for instance Glisson and James, 1992; Alter, 1990; Beatrice, 1990; Weiss, 1987). Community oriented researchers have examined collaboration as coalitions and consortia of development (Rosenthal and Mizrahi, 1994; Bailey and Koney, 1992; Sink and Stowers, 1989). Other researchers have examined community-based inter-organisational service delivery networks. However, although policymakers have identified networks as the most promising model for integrating services and strengthening poor communities, theorists such as Weiner (1990), Austin, (1991), and Alter and Hage (1993) have found the networks to be the most complex form of inter-organisational collaboration.

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Elizabeth A. Mulroy (1997) attempted an organisational analysis of an inter-organisational collaboration in which executive directors and frontline practitioners from seven agencies worked for five years to create, implement, and institutionalize a community-based service network of informal and formal family support programs to help prevent child abuse and neglect. She presents a theoretical framework for understanding community-based networks and inter-organisational collaboration. She describes and analyzes how collaboration was used as a method to build a new service network, the characteristics of the network, and factors that facilitated the collaborative process. In her study she found that a dense network of interpersonal and inter-organisational relationships was sustained and expanded throughout the lifecycle of the network although the transition to independent status was uncertain financially. She suggested development of a culture of mutual trust, building administrative infrastructure, starting with small network and growing incrementally for better inter-organisational collaboration practice.

Jennafer Kwait, Thomas W. Valente and David D. Celentano (2001) used social network analysis to understand inter-organisational relationships among HIV/AIDS service organisations in Baltimore. Their research work was based on varied factors like client referrals to other organisations, client referrals from other organisations, exchange of information about share clients, formal written linkage agreements for client referrals and joint programmes.

Danielle D'Amour et. al (2004) attempted a comparative analysis of inter-organisational collaboration and its effects in four health regions in Canada. They developed three-fold typology of collaboration viz., collaboration in action, collaboration under construction and collaboration in inertia to analyze the collaboration between professionals from different organizations. They concluded that the capacity of professionals to structure collective action determined the service continuity, service efficiency and responsiveness.

The literature on inter-organisational collaboration and networking came in general from the west. There are a few studies attempted in India as well. This may be due to the lack of popularity of this macro strategy among the members of voluntary sector. The few Indian works on this strategy concentrate on advantages and limitations of networking especially formal networks of VOs (Padali et. al 2003; Chandra, 2001; Tandon 1988) and a few concentrate on actual working of networks. But they hardly address the issues on the actual patterns of collaboration among the VOs at different level or between GOs and VOs as done in the west and structural constraints of the VOs at grassroots level. The present study addresses these research issues in the context of North East India where the proliferation and diversification of VOs was observed over the last decade.

The purpose of the present study is to analyse the patterns of collaboration and networking among the VOs on the one hand and between VOs and GOs on the other. As a backdrop to this in this study an attempt has been made to describe the characteristics of VOs, their organisational structure and pattern of service delivery. An attempt has also been made to identify the major constraints to interorganisational collaboration and networking among VOs from their leaders perspective. This study also tries to provide comprehensive accounts of two VOs who are successful in collaboration and networking.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is based on the primary data collected through structured questionnaire from the VOs functioning in Aizawl, the capital city of Mizoram state. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the information from the staff members of the VOs. A list of 30 active VOs in Aizawl city was compiled and the questionnaire was distributed to their key functionaries. After three repeated visits only 14 VOs responded positively. The collected data was processed and analysed by computer. Simple averages and per centage were used in analysis. In addition, sociograms were used to depict the pattern of collaboration. Apart from this quantitative approach

two case studies of successful VOs were attempted to discuss the dynamics of collaboration and networking.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section an attempt has been made to discuss the results of the data collected. The discussion has been structured into six parts. They are profile of respondents, profile of VOs surveyed, composition of governing boards of VOs, service users and target groups of VOs, collaboration patterns of VOs and constraints to inter organisational collaboration in social welfare and remedies.

Profile of Respondents: The personal characteristics of the respondents discussed as under include age, gender, and education, while the professional characteristics are education, special training, nature of training and experience in social welfare (see Table 1).

Table 1: Personal and Professional Profile of Respondents

SI.No	Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
N =14			
I	Mean Years of Age	30.14 ± 4.75	
II	Gender		
	Male	8	57.14
	Female	6	42.86
III	Mean Years of Education	16.07±2.43	
IV	Professional Education		
	None	2	14.29
	Social Work	4	28.57
	Psychology	3	21.43
	Social Sciences	4	28.57
	Medicine	1	7.14
V	Special Training	14	100.00
	None	6	42.86
	Short Term Courses	5	35.71
	Certificate	1	7.14
	PG	2	14.29
VI	Nature of Training		
	None	7	50.00
	Research/ PRA	3	21.43
	Mobilization and Organisation	2	14.29
	Administration	2	14.29
V	Mean Years of Experience in Social Welfare	4.10 ± 2.71	

Source: Computed

As regard to age most of the respondents are young. The mean age of the respondent's was worked out to 30.14 years. Most of the respondents were males. More than one-half of the respondents were male (57.14%) and more than one third were female (42.86%).

As regards education most of the respondents had higher education and completed at least a UG degree. The mean years of education of the respondents was worked out to 16.07. Interestingly, predominant majority of the respondents had professional education. More than three-fourth of them had professional qualification. Greater than one-fourth of the respondents had social work education (28.57%), greater than one-fifth had education in psychology (21.43%), and above one fourth had education in any other social science (28.57%), and one had educated in Medicine (7.14%).

All the respondents had some sort of training in social welfare though they were having different academic backgrounds. More than one-third of the respondents had short term courses (35.71%), and a few had certificate courses too. As regards the nature of training, more than one-fourth of the respondents had training in research or PRA (21.43%), and a few had training in Mobilisation and Organisation (14.29%), Administration (14.29%) and one-half had not undergone any training (50.00%), did not go for training in any field.

As regards the respondents' experience in social welfare, most of them had experience for a period less than 5 years. The mean years of experience in social welfare was worked out to 4.10 years.

Profile of VOs: The characteristics of the VOs discussed in the profile are legal status, duration of functioning and religious orientation (see Table 2).

Table 2: Profile of VOs

SI.No Characteristic Frequency Percentage
N =14

SI.No	Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
I	Legal Status		
	Unregistered	3	21.43
	Societies Registration Act	10	71.43
	Trust Act	1	7.14
II	Mean Years of Duration of Functioning	9 ± 9.39	
III	Religious Orientation		
	Christian	6	42.86
	Secular	8	57.14

Source: Computed Mean ± S.D.

As regards the legal status of VOs most of them were registered under Societies Registration Act. More than two thirds of the VOs (71.43%) were registered under Societies Registration Act of India. There was only 1 VO (7.14%) registered under Trust Act and a few were unregistered.

As regards the duration of functioning most of the VOs had experience in the field of social welfare over a decade. The mean years of duration of functioning of the VOs was worked out to 9 years.

The religious orientation of most of the VOs was reportedly secular. More than one-half of the VOs (57%) were secular while more than one-third were Christian (43%) in their religious orientation.

Composition of Governing Board of VOs: The composition of governing bodies in terms of gender and occupation would throw light on the power equations within the VOs. Hence, an attempt has been made to discuss the composition of the governing bodies of VOs in terms of gender and occupation (see Table 3).

Table 3: Composition of Governing Boards of NGOs

Sl.No	Category	Mean N =14	S.D
I Gender			
1	Number of Women	1.71 (32.43)	2.05
2	Number of Men	3.57 (67.57)	1.79
II Occupation/Profession			
3	Number of Professionals	1.93 (36.49)	1.38
4	Number of Theologians	0.64 (12.16)	1.01
5	Political Leaders	0.29 (5.41)	0.73
6	Officials	0.36 (6.76)	1.08
7	Business People	0.00 (0.00)	0.00
8	Number of Members in Governing Body	5.29 (100)	2.46

Source: Computed

As regards gender in patriarchal societies it is generally expected that men occupy the key positions in not only government organisations but also civil society organisations such as VOs. Hence, in the present study an attempt has been made to discuss the gender and occupational background of the members of the governing bodies of the VOs surveyed.

As regards gender most of the governing bodies of the VOs in Aizawl were male dominated. A typical VO had less than 6 members in its governing body. Of the six members 4 were reportedly men and less than 2 were women.

As regards the occupational background most of the members of the governing board of the studied VOs were professionals. Out of 6 members 2 were professionals, two out of four were theologians, one out of three were political leaders and one out of three were bureaucrats and none was a businessman.

Service Users and Target Groups of VOs: At the outset it was clear that those VOs surveyed were providers of social services to the disadvantaged sections of the society. The service users or the target groups of most of the VOs were children. More than one third of the

VOs surveyed were providing services to the children (43%). Drug users were next in the order of priority. Over one third of the VOs were providing services to drug users (39%). Women and sex workers were given next level of priority. Above one fourth of the organisations were serving them. The poor and marginalised (14%), the physically challenged (14.29%), HIV/AIDS patients (14.29%) and aged (7.14%) were the least served categories of the disadvantaged (see table 4).

Collaboration Pattern of VOs: Increasing emphasis on the partnership between the governmental and nongovernmental organisations as well as collaboration and networking among the VOs themselves has been laid in the national and international policy circles. Hence in the present study the patterns of collaboration were analysed from macro and micro perspectives. The macro picture of collaboration was analysed with the help of quantitative data while the microscopic picture is depicted with socio gram analysis.

Table 4: Service Users and Target Groups of NGOs

Sl.No	Service User	Frequency	Per centage
N =14			
1	Children	6	42.86
2	Women	4	28.57
3	Drug Users	4	28.57
4	Sex Workers	4	28.57
5	Poor and Marginalised	2	14.29
6	Disabled	2	14.29
7	HIV/ AIDS Patients	2	14.29
8	Aged	1	7.14

Source: Computed

Collaboration Pattern of VOs: Macro Picture: The pattern of collaboration of VOs with governmental organisations and departments at national and state levels, with CBOs at grassroots level, VOs at state, national and international levels were analysed and presented in table 5.

Partnership with state government was predominant among the VOs in Aizawl. 10 out of 14 VOs had support of Government Organisations. International VOs were in the next order, collaborating with VOs in Aizawl. Over 6 VOs i.e. more than half of them surveyed had the support of the International Nongovernmental Organisations (INGOs) like Indo-Global Social Service Society (IGSSS).

The other organisations with which the surveyed VOs collaborate include local VOs (51%), State Government Departments (47%), Mizoram SYNOD (43%), Central Government Departments (43%), National VOs (36%), Community Based VOs (36%), National Government Organisations (27%) and Educational Institutions (27%).

Table 5: Collaboration Patterns of NGOs

Sl.No	Type of Organisations	Frequency	Per centage
N =14			
1	State Government Organisations	10	71
2	International VOs	6	51

3	Local VOs	8	51
4	State Government Departments	4	47
5	National Government Departments	3	43
6	Mizoram SYNOD	3	43
7	National VOs	2	36
8	Community Based Organisations (CBOs)	2	36
9	Central Government Organisations	1	27
10	Educational Institutions	1	27

Source: Computed

Partnership with Government Organisations: Microscopic Picture: As revealed in the previous section the VOs had partnership with Government departments and Organisations. To probe further into the pattern of partnership a socio gram analysis was attempted (see Figure 1).

The major government organisations supporting voluntary action in Aizawl were Mizoram State AIDS Control Society (MSACS), National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) and Khadhi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC). Of these GOs, MSACS has reportedly funding one out of two VOs surveyed. NABARD has been supporting one out of four VOs.

Among the Government departments supporting VOs, department of social welfare and health were prominent. The social welfare department is supporting one out of four VOs while the health department supports one out of five VOs surveyed.

Figure 1: VOs Partnership with Government Departments and Organisations

Note: Sample VOs

Government Organisations or Departments

Among the VOs, VO2 had emerged as prominent in establishing and maintaining partnership with over six organisations. It has collaboration with state level government departments like DRDA, central government organisations like KVIC, NIRD and NABARD, and central government departments like Ministry of Rural Development.

VOs Collaboration with other Organisations: The surveyed VOs not only collaborate with governmental departments and organisations but with other VOs also. The sociogram depicts clearly that the international organisations UNODC-CHARCA and VOs like World Vision were the prominent organisations supporting the surveyed VOs (See Figure 2).

Of the VOs surveyed VO14, VO11, and VO4, were the prominent VOs who could collaborate with a number of other organisations. The organisation VO14 has been collaborating with other VOs like World Vision (WV), New Life Home Society, international projects like UNODC-CHARCA and community based VOs like YMA and MHIP. Similarly, VO11 was successful in collaborating with community based organisations like Young Mizo Association (YMA) and MHIP and ACI. The VO4 has been collaborating with VOs like Hope Care, World Vision (WV) Goodwill Foundation (GF) and Young Women Christian Association (YWCA).

Figure 2: Collaboration of VOs with Other Organisations

Note: Sample VOs

Other VOs

The microscopic picture of networking of VOs with governmental and other organisations indicated that most of the VOs have yet to establish and develop such collaboration relationships. Also apart from funding other types of collaboration such as joint programming, referral of clients have yet to develop in Mizoram. It is indeed very clear that most of the Aizawl based VOs are not yet familiar with the strategy of inter-organisational collaboration and networking.

Constraints to Inter-Organisational Collaboration and Suggestions: The novel strategy of networking has yet to become popular among the VOs in Mizoram. The question that arises here is why is it so? The respondents were asked to identify the major constraints to networking in Mizoram and their responses are presented in table 6.

It is very clear from their response that the VOs at present are hesitant in appreciating the concept of networking. Hence, the major constraints reported were lack of professionalism among VOs (36.31%), lack of Church involvement (36.31%), lack of transparency (26.73%), lack of trust (26.73%), Government's apathy towards VOs (36.31%) and no common platform for VOs to interact (26.73%).

The suggestions from the surveyed VOs were networking (46.88%), exchange of information (42.58%), development research (26.73%), establishment of common platform (26.73%) and Government support for networking (26.73%).

The constraints identified and suggestions offered by the VOs clearly demonstrate the need for training programmes for workers of the VOs on the strategy of collaboration and networking. The number of constraints identified and the emphasis on professionalism, networking, sharing of information etc underline the felt need for networking among the workers of the VOs. Yet, the question that arises here is that whether networking pays any dividend? To probe into the meaningfulness of networking and collaboration as a strategy of social welfare a few case studies on the two VOs are presented in the next section.

DYNAMICS OF COLLABORATION IN SOCIAL WELFARE: TWO CASE STUDIES

The previous discussion on the patterns of inter organisational collaboration among social welfare organisation in Aizawl revealed that by and large most of the Non governmental Organisations have not been successful in establishing and maintaining successful networking among themselves as well as with Governmental Organisations (GOs). In spite of this overall picture it was also observed that two VOs viz., VO2 and VO14 are respectively maintaining successful partnership with GOs and VOs. To understand further the dynamics of inter organisational collaboration as well as its effect on the functioning of VOs case studies of these two VOs based in Aizawl are presented in this chapter.

Table 6: Constraints to Inter organizational Collaboration in Social Welfare and Remedies

Sl.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
I	Constraints		
	Lack of Professionalism	2	36.31
	Lack of Church Involvement	2	36.31
	Government's Apathy over VOs	2	36.31
	Lack of Transparency	1	26.73
	Lack of Trust	1	26.73
	No Common Platform for VOs Interaction	1	26.73
II	Suggestions		
	Establishing formal Networks	4	46.88
	Exchange of Information	3	42.58

Research and Development	1	26.73
Establishment of Common Platform	1	26.73
Government Support for Networking	1	26.73

Source: Computed

Case 1: A VO Promoting Self Help Groups in Partnership with Government: The VO2 was established in 2004 and commenced its functioning in the same year. VO2 was registered under Societies Registration Act of 1986. Its orientation is toward Christian religion. The governing body has 7 members.

VO2 is an NGO, set up by like-minded people personally moved by the challenges of poverty and marginalisation in Mizo society. The organisation aims at the upliftment of the poor and marginalised sections of the Mizo society. After carefully studying the problems faced by the poor and marginalised, it decided to work on promoting SHGs as a most viable and practical strategy to eradicate poverty in the State. Ever since January 2004 it has been engaged in mobilisation and organisation of rural and urban poor through SHGs.

VO2 has been successful in establishing and maintaining partnership with the major Government departments and organisations involved in social welfare and development. The important GOs that are supporting VO2 work are DRDA and NABARD. Apart from these it has the support of CHARCA UNODC project. VOI is acting as a major facilitator of SHGs under SGSY scheme implemented by DRDA Aizawl district.

VO2 also links SHGs with Commercial Banks funding under the NABARD. From February 2004, VOI and NABARD started working together to facilitate quality SHGs. It recommends the SHGs that score above 80% in grading for loan from NABARD. Over Rs.5, 00,00,000/- has been already lent to the SHGs. It has also organised a number of training programmes for SHGs with NABARD's sponsorship. VO2 has also been closely working with Spices Board, Aizawl. So far with the Spices Board it has been conducting awareness campaigns and training programmes on pre and post-harvest techniques of spices in more than 50 villages. With their efforts a number of farmers have been sent to Cochin and other places for training in cultivation of spices.

Since, January 2004, VO2 has formed over 586 SHGs and the number of groups registered with it is increasing everyday. In fact the number of SHGs in Mizoram has increased significantly after the organisation's active involvement in this avenue. It has been conducting a number of awareness and training programmes for the SHGs. Most of the SHGs with it are moving from micro-credit stage to micro enterprise stage. It has been successful in facilitating the SHGs to achieve social and economic development through agricultural and allied activities. It has also been quite successful in ensuring markets to agricultural and allied products. Interestingly, the MSW students during the fieldwork observed that this VO could facilitate a number of SHGs to overcome poverty.

Case 2: A VO Promoting Mental Health in Collaboration with other Organisations: VO 14 is a voluntary non-profit organisation focusing on the mental health needs of the community. It was established on 23rd September 1992, and registered under Societies Registration Act XXI of 1860. It is the first and only mental health organisation in Mizoram.

The goal of VO14 is to intervene into the area of mental illness through prevention, care, support and creating an inclusive environment for the victims. VO14 mainly focuses on the sex workers, young women, young professional and peer educator. Their services towards the target

group are referral, counselling, recreational facilities, awareness, group educator, etc. Their sources of funding for these activities are MSACS, CHARCA -UNODC and UNIFEM.

VO14 is a major VO in Mizoram working on HIV/AIDS prevention and care. Besides its various other activities, it has undertaken a number of seminars, workshops, research projects and publications. Since May 2000, it has been running a Refuge Drop-in-Centre, a project of targeted intervention among the sex workers in Aizawl for the prevention and care of AIDS among them. The centre provides HIV/AIDS and STI testing, counselling, referrals to rehabilitation centres/half-way homes/moral education camps etc. Efforts are also being made for condom promotion and distribution, health management and consultations. The centre has been managed out of the fund received from Mizoram State AIDS Control Society (MSACS) and is functioning till date.

By increasing awareness about mental health among the general public the organisation responds to human suffering and distress caused by mental illness. It tries to inform the community about the potential and the capacity of people with mental illness so that illness mitigation and management are made possible. It actively supports the rights of the people with mental illness and strives towards their holistic development by listening, befriending, counselling, educating, providing health care, imparting skills and above all advocating on their behalf whenever needed.

CONCLUSIONS

The voluntary sector is emerging in the simple society of Mizoram in the wake of socio – economic development and modernisation. Very interestingly, most of the VOs were registered (under Societies Registration Act), have been functioning over 10 years, are secular in their orientation (in a predominantly Christian Society where religion is exerting maximum influence on social life) and their governing boards are filled in by a large number of professionals. Yet, the governing structures of VOs reflect the patrilineal social structure of the Mizo society and a few women have representation. A wide variety of service users of the VOs were observed and the prominent being children While, women, drug users, sex workers, have attracted a significant number of VOs. But the poor and marginalised, disabled, HIV/AIDS patients and aged have yet to catch the attention of this emerging sector.

As regards collaboration the State Government Organisations have the greatest number of collaborations with the surveyed VOs, followed by local VOs, International VOs, and State Government Departments. But collaboration with Faith- based Organisations (FBOs), Community-based Organisations (CBOs), Central Government Organisations and Academic Institutions have yet to develop.

Unfortunately still most of the VOs have yet to establish collaborative relations with other organisations. Also apart from funding other types of collaboration such as joint programming, referral of clients have yet to develop in Mizoram. Though there is a felt need among the workers of VOs for collaboration it is very striking that most of the VOs are not familiar with the strategies of interorganisational collaboration and networking. The most important constraints in networking among organisations in social welfare from the point of view of leaders of VOs were lack of professionalism, lack of church involvement, and Government's apathy towards VOs.

SUGGESTIONS

From the results of the present study a few suggestions for those interested in social welfare and social development, especially for the government and voluntary sector at multilevel.

- | The low level of networking among the social welfare organisations could be attributed to infancy of voluntary sector. It could also be due to the lack of common values orientation in the voluntary sector. If such a value orientation emerges in the voluntary sector there will be spirit of networking and collaboration among the organisations. The realisation of common interests goals and values among the leaders and better interpersonal relations among them would pave the way for cohesive networks of organisations and GO and NGO partnerships too. Towards this they need to have a common platform for their interaction and dialogue.
- | VOs need to have mutual trust and come forward in sharing and exchanging of information about the social welfare concerns and issues.
- | The VOs need to infuse professionalism in their functioning. Recruitment of professional social workers and in – service training to the existing staff may be the two options available to the VOs.
- | The VOs need to collaborate with the academic institutions especially social work and social science departments for conducting in-service training programmes for their workers where the strategy of networking needs to be adequately emphasized.
- | The VOs themselves need to identify specific fields so as to form formal networks and have better collaboration.
- | A few VOs collaborate with the widespread and crucial community based organisations in Mizoram like YMA, MHIP, and MUP. Joint programming with them at community level would be fruitful and successful as demonstrated by the two successful VOs in the state.
- | Government policy also needs to emphasise the collaboration and networking of VOs and suitable incentives need to be designed and provided at national and state levels.
- | National level VOs shall come forward to conduct orientation programmes on networking and collaboration at the grassroot and state level VOs. In this effort they can network with social work, management and social science departments.

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